

ISic1429

I.Sicily inscription 1429

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, private collection

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI301119

1. ἄ Μεθούλ-

2. ο̅ θυγάτε̅ρ

3.

Edition: PHI336184

1. Ἄνεφθούλ-

2. ε̅ θυγάτε̅ρ

3. Κλε̅ταγό-

4. ρα Δου σ̅ [.] -

5. α.

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284832

EDCS 64600168

PHI 301119

PHI 336184

Bibliography

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